

Benzoylacetylaldehyde as a Gravimetric Reagent for Uranium(VI)

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Uranium(VI) has been determined gravimetrically with benzoylacetylaldehyde. The orange-red complex, $\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_2)_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, is precipitated in the pH-range 6.0-6.6, adjusted with pyridine and is weighed as such, after drying at 110° . Separation of UO_2^{2+} from Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Th^{4+} , VO^{2+} or MoO_4^{2-} has been effected by precipitating the complex in presence of magnesium-EDTA, while sulphosalicylic acid has been used to mask Be^{2+} or Zr^{4+} . The relative standard deviation is 0.04% and the mean relative error is $\pm 0.14\%$. The uranium content of some samples of its ores have also been determined.

A CRITICAL examination¹ of the important gravimetric methods for the determination of Uranium(VI) indicates that the reagents used are mostly oxygen-containing and the complexes formed are often of indefinite composition or the procedures have poor selectivity. Benzoylacetylaldehyde, a reagent utilised in the gravimetric and/or spectrophotometric estimation of beryllium², titanium(IV)², mercury(II)³, vanadium(IV)³, molybdenum(VI)⁴, aluminium⁵ and iron(III)⁵ has been found to be an excellent precipitant for uranium(VI). The orange-red colour of the complex has been utilised in the spectrophotometric determination of uranium(VI) after extracting in isobutyl methyl ketone⁶. In the present investigation conditions have been set to precipitate the thermally stable complex of definite composition, $\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_2)_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ quantitatively in the pH-range 6.0-6.6 controlled by pyridine. The complex has been weighed after drying at 110° . In the presence of magnesium-ethylenediamine tetraacetate (Mg-EDTA) the procedure is very selective for uranium(VI) and the metal can be determined in its ores without prior separations.

Experimental

Benzoylacetylaldehyde: The reagent was prepared in the laboratory² and an ethanolic solution was used. **Uranium(VI) solution**: Uranyl nitrate (B.D.H.) solution was purified by precipitation with ammonia in the presence of disodium-EDTA. The precipitate was washed with water, dissolved in nitric acid and diluted. The metal content was determined gravimetrically using standard procedures. The final solution contained 39.88 mg of the metal per 5 ml.

Diverse ions: Aqueous solutions of the desired metal ions were prepared from nitrates, chlorides or sulphates. A few drops of a suitable acid was added to prevent hydrolysis where necessary.

Pyridine solution: A 20% aqueous solution of freshly distilled pyridine was prepared and used for adjusting the pH. This solution could be used for one month when stored in coloured bottles.

Mg-EDTA solution: Solutions of disodium-EDTA (Titriplex III, E. Merck) and magnesium chloride, each of 0.1 M strength were prepared separately; 20 ml portions of each were mixed when magnesium-EDTA was used as the masking agent.

Apparatus: A battery-operated bench model Cambridge pH-meter was used to measure the acidity.

Procedure: To an aliquot of uranium(VI) solution containing 20 to 45 mg of the metal, ammonium hydroxide (1 M) was added dropwise until the colour became faint yellow. The solution was diluted to 150 ml, heated to boiling and benzoylacetylaldehyde (0.15 to 0.25 g) dissolved in aqueous ethanol (~15 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. The pH of the mixture was then raised to 6.0-6.6 by the addition of aqueous pyridine (20%). The yellow uranium(VI)-benzoylacetylaldehyde complex was slowly formed, which on digestion on a hot water-bath for 1 hr was coagulated into an easily filtrable orange-red form. The precipitate was filtered through a sintered glass crucible of fine porosity, washed with hot water (70° - 80°) and weighed as $\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_2)_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ after drying at 110° - 120° . The factor for the metal in the complex was 0.3045. Alternatively, the complex could be converted into U_3O_8 by ignition taking usual precautions before weighing. The results of these determinations are given in Table I.

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions: A 5 ml portion of the stock uranium(VI) solution was mixed with a known quantity of the desired foreign metal ion and the pH was raised to about 4.2 with aqueous ammonia (1 M). The mixture was diluted to 150 ml after adding 20 ml of 0.1 M EDTA solution and heated to boiling. The reagent solution was added cautiously with stirring. A 20 ml portion of 0.1 M magnesium chloride solution was added and the pH was raised to 6.0 to 6.6 with dropwise addition of aqueous pyridine solution maintaining the mixture at near boiling condition. The precipitate of uranium(VI)-benzoylacetylaldehyde was allowed to stand for 1 hr on

TABLE 1. DETERMINATION OF URANIUM

U taken, mg	Wt. of complex, mg	U found, mg	Rel. Error, %
23.98	78.84	24.00	+0.08
	78.79	23.99	+0.04
25.89	85.10	25.90	+0.04
	85.08	25.90	+0.04
39.88	131.4	40.00	+0.30
	131.4	40.00	+0.30
43.15	141.9	43.20	+0.11
	141.6	43.11	-0.09

a hot water-bath and it was filtered, washed, dried and weighed as before. Thus uranium(VI) could be separated from and determined in the presence of lead(II), bismuth(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), chromium(III), iron(III), aluminium(III), cerium(III), thorium(IV), vanadium(IV) or molybdenum(VI).

Uranium(VI) could also be precipitated with benzoylacetylacetonide and separated from beryllium(II) and zirconium(IV) when 0.5 g of sulphosalicylic acid was used instead of magnesium-EDTA solution. The results of these separations are given in Table 2.

TABLE 3. DETERMINATION OF URANIUM IN ORES

Sample	U ₃ O ₈ found,	
	Standard method	Given method
Canadian Uraninite	52.51%	52.46% 52.56%
Indian Uraninite	24.70%	24.76% 24.59%

Procedure for the determination of uranium in ores : About 500 mg of the ore was treated first with dilute nitric acid and then with 5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid. The mixture was carefully evaporated to dryness, cooled and diluted with sufficient amount of water to dissolve the most of the uranium present. The residue was filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter paper and ignited in a platinum crucible. The mass left was treated first with a few drops of hydrofluoric acid and then with 5 N nitric acid. It was filtered, the filtrate was mixed with the first filtrate and the volume was made up to 250 ml.

Uranium was determined taking a proper aliquot (25-75 ml) of this stock solution following the procedure described above. In these determinations, 40 ml of 0.1 M-EDTA and 40 ml of magnesium chloride were used and the amount of benzoylacetylacetonide was 0.2 g in 15 ml ethanol. The results of these determinations are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 2. SEPARATION OF URANIUM(VI) FROM DIVERSE IONS (U taken = 39.88 mg)

Diverse ion added, mg	Masking agent	Wt. of complex, mg	U found, mg	Rel. Error, %
Be ²⁺ , 20	(a)	131.3	39.97	+0.22
		131.0	39.88	-0.02
Co ²⁺ , 50	(b)	131.4	40.00	+0.30
		131.1	39.91	+0.08
Ni ²⁺ , 30	(b)	131.4	40.00	+0.30
		131.3	39.97	+0.22
Pb ²⁺ , 20	(b), (c)	130.7	39.78	-0.24
		130.8	39.81	-0.18
Bi ³⁺ , 20	(b)	131.1	39.91	+0.08
		131.0	39.88	-0.02
Fe ³⁺ , 40	(b)	130.7	39.78	-0.24
		131.3	39.97	+0.22
Al ³⁺ , 20	(b)	131.2	39.94	+0.14
		131.4	40.00	+0.30
Cr ³⁺ , 50	(b)	131.3	39.97	+0.22
		130.7	39.78	-0.24
Ce ³⁺ , 50	(b)	131.1	39.91	+0.08
		131.4	40.00	+0.30
Th ⁴⁺ , 50	(b)	130.9	39.84	-0.10
		131.3	39.97	+0.22
VO ²⁺ , 30	(b)	131.4	40.00	+0.30
		131.2	39.94	+0.14
Zr ⁴⁺ , 40	(a)	131.2	39.94	+0.14
		130.8	39.81	-0.18
MoO ₄ ²⁻ , 30	(b)	131.0	39.88	-0.02
		131.1	39.91	+0.08

(a) Sulphosalicylic acid, (b) Mg-EDTA, (c) Ammonium acetate

Results and Discussion

Properties and composition of the complex :

The complex when first precipitated was of yellowish orange in colour, but on digestion changed to orange-red. The orange-red form of the complex was analysed for uranium by oxidation of a weighed quantity to U₃O₈ and for nitrogen by Kjeldahl's (micro) method. The results, U, 30.48% (theo., 30.45%) and N, 3.53% (theo., 3.58%) indicated the formula to be UO₂(C₁₅H₁₂O₂N)₂·2H₂O which is analogous to the uranium(VI)-complex of benzoyl-*m*-nitro acetanilide⁷ and various other octacoordinated uranium(VI) complexes^{8,9}. The complex was found to be stable up to 195° and decomposed with a vigorous reaction above this temperature. Uranium(VI)-benzoylacetylacetonide was soluble in most common organic solvents, though practically insoluble in 20% aqueous ethanol.

Effect of the concentration of the reagent :

Precipitation of uranium(VI) was carried out at pH 6.5 using different amounts of benzoylacetylacetonide

maintaining all other conditions same. It was observed that the supernatant liquid after the precipitation of uranium should be 0.04–0.14% with respect to the reagent for the quantitative estimation of the metal. The results were marginally high when more reagent was used.

Effect of pH : Experimental studies on the determination of uranium(VI) in solutions of different pH-values with all the other factors identical revealed that the precipitation commenced at pH 5.0 and was quantitative in the range 6.0–6.6.

Effect of sequestering agents :

The presence of sulphosalicylic acid and magnesium-EDTA did not interfere with the precipitation of uranium(VI) with benzoylacetylacetonide. However, disodium-EDTA, citrate, tartrate and phosphate inhibited the precipitation.

Precision and Accuracy :

The average relative error in the determination of uranium(VI) by the procedure described was 0.14% while the relative standard deviation was $\pm 0.18\%$.

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